

Research papers

Influence of soil organic matter on stable water isotope analysis of soil pore water using the $\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{liquid})\text{--}\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{vapor})$ vapor equilibration method

Devakunjari Vadibeler^{a,b}, Michael P. Stockinger^{b,*}, Leonard I. Wassenaar^c,
Christine Stumpp^b

^a School of Geography, University of Leeds, Leeds LS2 9JT, United Kingdom

^b BOKU University, Institute of Soil Physics and Rural Water Management (SoPhy), Department of Landscape, Water and Infrastructure, Muthgasse 18, 1190 Vienna, Austria

^c Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Ottawa, 25 Templeton St., Ottawa, ON K1N 6N5 Canada

ARTICLE INFO

This manuscript was handled by Marco Borga, Editor-in-Chief, with the assistance of Daniele Penna, Associate Editor

Keywords:

Direct liquid–vapor equilibration method
Volumetric water content
Soil organic matter

ABSTRACT

The direct liquid–vapor equilibration (DLVE) method is commonly used to analyze the stable isotope composition of soil pore water ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) by laser spectroscopy. The influence of soil texture, soil volumetric water content (VWC), and the presence of organic matter impacting reliable results is not yet fully understood. We conducted two different experiments: in the first experiment, natural silty topsoil with 4 % organic matter, chemically washed soil with 1 % organic matter, and two non-organic sediments (sand and kaolinite) were used to study the impact of soil organic matter on the DLVE method for a gradient of volumetric porewater contents. In the second experiment, different concentrations of humic acids were mixed with sandy sediment and porewater of known isotopic composition to investigate whether organic matter alone or its interactions with the sediment impacted the DLVE measurements. Results showed an influence of VWC on measured vapor isotope compositions, especially during drier conditions, with an unexpected lower accuracy (larger bias from the known isotope ratio) for sandy sediment compared to kaolinite when VWC was below $0.15 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Besides VWC and soil texture, organic matter additionally altered the expected vapor isotope composition, as natural silty topsoil with 4 % organic matter showed lower accuracy at all volumetric water contents than the silty soil with only 1 % organic matter. Results of the second experiment showed that humic acids were significantly ($p < 0.05$) influencing DLVE outcomes regardless of the humic acid concentrations for the soil–water mixture samples, with a threshold behavior of markedly decreased accuracy above 2 % humic acid concentration for both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$. As pure mixtures of water and humic acid generally had higher accuracy, the interaction of humic acid with the soil might be a factor. A multivariate regression analysis was carried out using volumetric water content and soil organic matter as independent variables to correct for biases. While for oxygen isotopes the results could be improved, hydrogen isotopes still showed low accuracy especially under dry conditions and larger percentages of humic acid. Our findings indicate that in addition to soil texture and volumetric water content, the interaction between the soil matrix and organic matter probably affects the DLVE method measurements, particularly at concentrations exceeding 0.1 g of humic acid per ml of water. In certain instances, this interaction may be corrected, thus addressing existing methodological gaps.

1. Introduction

Oxygen ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) and hydrogen ($\delta^2\text{H}$) isotopes of soil water are used as tracers to study hydrological processes in the soil–plant–atmosphere continuum, also referred to as the “critical zone” (Sprenger et al., 2016; Stumpp et al., 2018; Sprenger et al., 2019), e.g., they allow determinations of plant source water (Liu et al., 2011; Orłowski et al.,

2018), groundwater recharge (Koeniger et al., 2016; Chesnaux and Stumpp, 2018), movement and mixing of water in geological media (Benettin et al., 2022), transit times in soils (Stumpp et al., 2009), partitioning of evapotranspiration (Hogan et al., 2020; Liebhard et al., 2022), and ecohydrological partitioning of precipitation (Landgraf et al., 2022). Obtaining representative samples for porewater isotopic analysis is difficult, as soils are highly heterogeneous due to variations in

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: michael_stockinger@boku.ac.at (M.P. Stockinger).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2025.134081>

Received 11 September 2024; Received in revised form 4 June 2025; Accepted 12 August 2025

Available online 14 August 2025

0022-1694/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

structure, texture, moisture content, microbial activity, rooting patterns, and organic matter compositions, all of which significantly influence porewater movement and availability within soil profiles (Beyer et al., 2020). However, the ability to accurately measure $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ in saturated and unsaturated soils is critically important for developing integrated and effective approaches to soil water resource management and addressing global water scarcity (Kübert et al., 2020). For example, accurate isotope measurements enable an understanding of the complex biogeochemical interactions between soil, organic matter, and plant species, supporting sustainable agroforestry management and helping to identify potential risks to water and food security under changing environmental conditions (Smith, 2008). Due to the widespread use of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ in critical zone hydrology, it is crucial to accurately measure porewater isotopes to minimize uncertainties and account for the potential influence of soil characteristics and various measurement protocols on the results. Among these soil characteristics, Ceperley et al. (2024) highlight that one remaining issue in measuring $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ is the potential influence of organic matter on measurement results.

The measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ isotopes of soil and porewater is often carried out using laser spectrometers or isotope mass spectrometers that require liquid water samples, necessitating the extraction of soil water from a soil sample. Various extraction methods such as lysimeters, mechanical squeezing, and centrifugation are used to assess the pore water isotope composition (Sprenger et al., 2015a). These methods are costly (lysimeters, centrifuges), laborious (mechanical squeezing), and incapable of extracting all the pore water in soils especially at low water contents (Sprenger et al., 2015a). Hence, an alternative is the direct liquid–vapor equilibration (DLVE) method which does not extract water but equilibrates $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ of soil pore water to headspace vapor under closed system conditions prior to analyzing the water vapor using a laser spectrometer (Wassenaar et al., 2008). A soil sample is placed into a gas-tight resealable sampling bag which is inflated with dry air and left to reach isotopic equilibrium between the soil pore water and headspace vapor under closed-system conditions. The headspace vapor is then sampled using cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) or off-axis integrated cavity output spectroscopy (OA-ICOS). The isotope composition of the soil pore water can be calculated based on temperature-dependent equilibrium isotope fractionation processes and by running water standards with known isotope composition for scale normalization. In the last 15 years, aspects of the application of the DLVE method were improved. For example, different resealable sampling bags were tested (Hendry et al., 2015), with food-grade Ziploc® bags being one of the most viable and cost-effective options to date (Wassenaar et al., 2008; Hendry et al., 2011). Biogenic gases, methane (CH_4), and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) may evolve from the samples which are known to contaminate isotope measurements using the DLVE method (Hendry et al., 2011). To overcome this, Gralher et al. (2018) found that inflating the sampling bags (using metallized bags in their study) with dry air instead of nitrogen gas and applying post-processing data corrections reduced the potential influence of these VOC gases. The issue of VOC was further found when the DLVE method was extended to plant samples (roots, stems, leaves, and fruits) (Santos Pires et al., 2022). Recently, an autosampler was developed for the DLVE method (Pyschik et al., 2025).

Besides issues related to VOC, other studies considered different equilibration times for different soil textures at various water contents (Garvelmann et al., 2012; Mueller et al., 2014; Sprenger et al., 2015b; Hendry et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2019). Vadibeler et al. (2022) found that 24 h was ideal for 40 % saturated sandy soil and 100 % saturated kaolinite. However, 48 h was needed for kaolinite when the saturation level was reduced to 40 %, but the influence of lower soil saturation levels was not tested. Orłowski et al. (2016b) concluded that DLVE could be used in comparison with other extraction techniques only at gravimetric water contents > 20 % and for coarse soils.

Previous studies also highlighted that different methods target different water pools, and the presence of organic materials resulted in

reduced accuracy (Barbeta et al., 2019; Martín-Gómez et al., 2015; Orłowski et al., 2016b; West et al., 2010). Martín-Gómez et al. (2015) showed that ethanol and methanol contaminated the isotope measurements using isotope-ratio infrared spectroscopy. They suggested a post-processing correction scheme of isotope measurements for samples with small amounts of ethanol and methanol contamination, conducted using a Micro-Combustion-Module™ (MCM); (Picarro, 2024). However, this still resulted in low accuracies.

Orłowski et al. (2016a) indicated that the presence of soil organic matter might also influence the required equilibration time and accuracy of the DLVE method due to the availability of exchangeable bonded hydrogen (Meißner et al., 2014). Similarly, Vadibeler et al. (2022) showed that silty soil with 2 % organic carbon content required a longer 96 h equilibration time, whereas silty soil with 4 % organic carbon content did not reach isotope equilibration within 168 h regardless of the soil water saturation level. These findings support the hypothesis that soil matrix forces and particulate organic matter might alter particle interfacial chemistry and soil wettability, which also might influence the isotope equilibration fractionation processes under closed system conditions (Gaj et al., 2018; 2019). These previous studies highlight some complications introduced by variable soil organic matter with the application of the DLVE method and some have encouraged focusing on this problem because of the lack of clear evidence (Adams et al., 2020; Ceperley et al., 2024).

The objective of this study was to better understand the influence of different proportions of soil organic matter, as well as the effects of soil and organic matter interactions, on the DLVE method. To achieve this, we conducted controlled experiments to (a) test the accuracy (or bias as the difference between known and measured) of the DLVE method when using soils of different textures, volumetric water contents (VWC), and with different organic matter contents (OM), (b) investigate if possible organic matter influences stem from organic matter by itself or from its interaction with the soil matrix, and (c) develop a multiple regression model of the possible impact of VWC and OM.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Soil selection

Four soil samples with different textures and organic matter content were used (Table 1): sandy sediment, pure kaolinite, and silty loam topsoil with 4 % and 1 % organic matter, respectively. The non-organic sandy sediment contained 30 % fine gravel, 69 % sand, and 1 % of silt and clay mixture. The silty loam topsoil (from Obersiebenbrunn, Austria) was made up of 25 % sand, 63 % silt, and 12 % clay. The non-organic kaolinite was 100 % clay. The organic matter of a subsample of the silty loam soil was altered using a carbon removal method to create the same soil but with only 1 % organic matter (as described in Section 2.2). Details about the soil textures and organic matter analyses are in Vadibeler et al. (2022). All soil samples were broken down into smaller

Table 1
Properties of soil samples used in this study.

Soil source	Soil texture	Soil composition				Organic matter (%)
		Gravel (%)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	
Gravel pit, Bruckmühl, Germany	Sandy	30	69	0.5	0.5	0
Topsoil, Obersiebenbrunn, Austria	Silty loam	0	25	63	12	4
Topsoil, Obersiebenbrunn, Austria	Silty loam	0	25	63	12	1
Kaolinite, Carl Roth GmbH	Clay	0	0	0	100	0

pieces using a mortar and pestle and oven-dried for three days at 105 °C before re-wetting them with two reference waters of known H and O isotope compositions. To minimize possible isotopic changes due to condensation or evaporative fractionation, the water was quickly (<5 min) added to the oven-dried samples, and the bags were immediately sealed. Tests with 105 °C oven-dried soils and an added volumetric water content of 7.5 % showed that the isotopic deviations due to evaporative fractionation after five minutes were negligible (<0.5 ‰) and that condensation was non-existent.

2.2. Carbon removal

The oven-dried silty topsoil was chemically treated to oxidize organic matter using hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) (30 % w/w: Carl and Roth GmbH). The H₂O₂ used was analytical grade. 20 mL of water was added to every 5 mL of H₂O₂ for every 40 g of soil sample while heating and stirring the mixtures. The soil washing process was stopped after 30 days when the evolution of CO₂ gas bubbles stopped, assuming that most of the organic matter had been removed as carbon dioxide.

2.3. Experimental design

2.3.1. Experiment 1 – natural organic matter in soils

This experiment examined the influence of natural soil organic matter and low volumetric water content on pore water isotope measurements using the DLVE method. Non-organic sandy sediment and kaolinite were studied along with the silty loam topsoil with 4 % organic matter and chemically washed similar topsoil with 1 % organic matter to compare results to different soil textures free of organic matter. Sub-samples of these oven-dried sediments were filled individually in 100 cm³ sampling rings and re-wetted to seven different volumetric water contents typically found in natural soils (0.46 cm³ cm⁻³, 0.45 cm³ cm⁻³, 0.44 cm³ cm⁻³, 0.41 cm³ cm⁻³, 0.35 cm³ cm⁻³, 0.15 cm³ cm⁻³, and 0.06 cm³ cm⁻³). These different volumetric water contents were chosen to cover the entire range of soil moisture in the natural silty soil collected from Obersiebenbrunn as indicated by water retention curves, which were obtained using the HYPROP system (data not shown) (Version 4.2.0, METEER Group AG, 2017).

Two control waters ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -11.2 \text{ ‰}$, $\delta^2\text{H} = -77.8 \text{ ‰}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O} = -13.7 \text{ ‰}$, $\delta^2\text{H} = -104.3 \text{ ‰}$) were used to re-wet the oven-dried samples in the individual sampling rings. The sampling rings were later (< 5 min) removed, and the re-wetted samples were placed in resealable bags for pore water isotope analysis using the DLVE method (see section 2.4). To ensure uniform wetting, soil samples were manually mixed by shaking and gently squeezing the bags. Additionally, the presence of biogenic gas interferences was determined with the CH₄ and residual values recorded by the Picarro analyzer.

2.3.2. Experiment 2 – Humic acid in soil and water

This experiment examined the influence of different concentrations of organic matter in soil–water and water mixtures on the isotope pore water analysis using the DLVE method. Technical grade humic acid (53680-50G, Sigma-Aldrich®) was used to represent organic matter in soil samples. Commercially available humic acid was used to ensure the identical preparation of synthetic organic samples in the laboratory for reliable data comparison. Humic acid was mixed with water only (HAW) or with water and sandy sediment (HAS). Sandy sediment was used because it was free of any natural organic matter and easier to handle, unlike silty or clayey soils.

First, 79.9 g, 79.6 g, 79.2 g, 78.4 g, and 76.2 g of oven-dried non-organic sandy sediment was mixed with 0.08 g, 0.4 g, 0.8 g, 1.6 g, and 3.8 g of humic acid, respectively. This was done to prepare HAS samples with 0.1 %, 0.5 %, 1.0 %, 2.0 %, and 5.0 % organic matter sequentially. These concentrations (%) of humic acid represent the expected ratios of organic matter in natural soil samples (Biernbaum, 2012). Then, de-aerated water ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -11.1 \text{ ‰}$, $\delta^2\text{H} = -75.7 \text{ ‰}$) of different volumes

(30 cm³, 28 cm³, 26 cm³, 17.5 cm³, 5.5 cm³, and 1.2 cm³) were individually added to each of the HAS samples prepared earlier. The humic acid concentrations (g humic acid/cm³ water) in HAS samples were calculated to be in the range between 0.003 g cm⁻³ to 3.333 g cm⁻³. Three replicates of each combination were prepared and analyzed. All HAS samples were placed into resealable bags and analyzed using the DLVE method (see section 2.4).

HAW samples were prepared by mixing different amounts of humic acid (0.08 g, 0.4 g, 0.8 g, 1.6 g, and 3.8 g) with different volumes (30 cm³, 28 cm³, 26 cm³, 17.5 cm³, 5.5 cm³, and 1.2 cm³) of de-aerated water ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -11.1 \text{ ‰}$, $\delta^2\text{H} = -75.7 \text{ ‰}$), respectively. These relative mixtures had similar humic acid concentrations as calculated for the HAS samples. Three replicates of each combination were prepared for analysis to reduce experimental error and improve the accuracy of the results. The pH values of the HAW mixtures were measured using a pH meter (Multi 3420, Wissenschaftlich-Technische Werkstätten GmbH, 2011), and the mixtures were put into resealable bags for the headspace vapor analysis (see section 2.4).

2.4. Stable isotope analysis using direct-liquid vapor equilibration (DLVE)

All the prepared samples in both experimental setups were analyzed using the classic DLVE method. The samples were placed into Ziploc® brand Double Guard freezer bags with Double Zipper Seal (~1 L volume) (S. C. Johnson & Sons Inc., USA). The bags were inflated with dry air and tightly sealed for soil pore water-vapour or water-vapour equilibration. The initial mass of the bags before equilibration was recorded ($\pm 0.01 \text{ g}$) and all bags were double bagged using 3 L Toppits® brand freezer bags (Melitta Gesellschaft GmbH, Salzburg, Austria) as suggested by Wassenaar et al. (2008) to prevent air loss. Following the initial study by Wassenaar et al. (2008), all the samples were equilibrated isothermally for three days. Because temperature controls the isotope fractionation (Majoube, 1971), the sample handling, equilibration, and analysis were carried out isothermally at $22 \pm 0.5 \text{ °C}$. Two different standard water samples of 5 mL were similarly prepared alongside the samples to correct the instrumental drift. After three days, the resealable bags were re-weighed before analysis, and the masses of the bags were recorded to calculate the percentage of water loss from each during equilibration. Then, the headspace vapor was analyzed through an injection needle using a CRDS laser analyzer (L2130-i, Picarro, Inc., 2020). The measurements were reported in per mil (‰) relative to Vienna Standard Mean Ocean Water (VSMOW). Based on the initial procedure by Wassenaar et al. (2008), the measurements were made in the sequence of standard 1, sample 1, sample 2, sample 3, and standard 2 for drift correction and normalization. The measurements took between four to ten minutes until standard deviations (SDs) of < 0.5 ‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and < 1.0 ‰ for $\delta^2\text{H}$ isotopes were reached, during which the bags still contained enough headspace for sampling. The last 60 s of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ readings were averaged and recorded as δ_f to represent the final isotope measurements. Subsequently, a linear regression between the known isotope values of the liquid standard waters and the measured isotope ratios of the standard water's headspace vapor in equilibrium was used to convert the measured vapor isotope ratios of the samples into their corresponding liquid isotope values. During analysis, the water vapor concentration for all samples was relatively constant, ranging between 31,000–35,000 ppmV, being below the 45,000 ppm upper limit of water vapor concentration for measurement with the Picarro laser spectroscope. Hence, water vapor concentration did not alter the isotope measurements obtained, and there was no need to dilute or correct the samples. To evaluate measurement accuracy, z-scores were used, similar to Wassenaar et al. (2012) who compared the accuracy (bias) of isotope-ratio mass spectrometry and laser absorption spectroscopy. First, the known isotope compositions of the reference waters (δ_i) were subtracted from δ_f to determine the isotopic deviation ($\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) between the initially used and finally analyzed isotope ratios of the pore water/water. The calculated $\Delta\delta$ values were positive when the measured

isotope values were enriched compared to the reference water used. Accordingly, the calculated $\Delta\delta$ values were negative when the measurements were depleted. Then, $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ were divided by the target standard deviation ($\pm 0.5\text{‰}$ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\pm 1.0\text{‰}$ for $\delta^2\text{H}$) to calculate their z-score (z_{O} for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and z_{H} for $\delta^2\text{H}$). The measured isotope value was an accurate measurement for $-2 < \text{z-score} < +2$ (Wassenaar et al., 2012). On the contrary, measurements were not accurate for z-scores outside these boundaries. Both $\Delta\delta$ values and z-scores were used in data analyses for different purposes (see 2.5 Analyses of data).

2.5. Analyses of data

Results from the replicates are presented as mean values along with their respective standard deviations (SDs). For both experimental setups, scatterplots and linear regressions of the isotopic deviations $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ were used to illustrate the isotope fractionation process in the resealable bags for different soil textures with and without organic matter. A meteoric water line (WL) with a slope of 8.45 (based on the equilibrium fractionation factors at 20 °C; Majoube, 1971) was added to these scatterplots to check for possible kinetic fractionation effects that would indicate e.g., biological or chemical reactions occurring in the sampling bags. The measurement accuracies as impacted by soil textures, volumetric water content, and organic matter content were evaluated using scatterplots between the respective influencing soil characteristic and z-scores. Lastly, specifically for experiment 2, a scatterplot of humic acid concentration (mg/mL) and z-scores was used to investigate the impact of adding different humic acid concentrations to pure water (HAW) or water-soil mixtures (HAS). This was complemented by a two-sample *t*-test to compare $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ measured from HAW and HAS samples to study the significance of the interaction between soil and organic matter mixtures. The impact of organic matter in the resealable bags with HAW and HAS samples was considered to have a significant effect on the isotope measurements when $p < 0.05$.

2.6. Data correction

This study was not specifically designed to correct biased results. However, we tested if a correction would be possible with a multivariate regression analysis that was carried out to predict the $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ values based on the influence of two independent variables, i.e., soil organic matter (OM) and volumetric water content (VWC) (Eq. (1)). The predicted values were then subtracted from the measured $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ to calculate the $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{calculated}}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{calculated}}$ values (Eq. (2)), which were then transformed to z_{O} and z_{H} scores. The influence of soil organic matter and volumetric water content were considered significant when $p < 0.05$.

$$\Delta\delta_{\text{predicted}} = a_1\text{OM} + a_2\text{VWC} + b \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\delta_{\text{calculated}} = \Delta\delta_{\text{measured}} - \Delta\delta_{\text{predicted}} \quad (2)$$

where 'a_n' and 'b' are the regression coefficients and intercept, respectively.

3. Results

The mean water loss from all the resealable bags measured after three days in both experimental set-ups was negligible ($< 0.2\%$) (data not shown). Hence, water loss and evaporative enrichment from the bags was insignificant. Moreover, the CH_4 and residuals values recorded by the Picarro analyzer indicated that the isotope deviations were not influenced by biogenic gas interferences (Fig. S1, supplementary material).

3.1. Experiment 1 – natural organic matter in soils

There were no pronounced differences in $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ for all soil

samples caused by different reference waters used to re-wet them (Fig. 1, Fig. 2). Hence, any difference in isotope ratios between reference water and actual measured values are independent of the initial isotope ratios and were influenced by different soil texture and soil volumetric water contents. Based on a plot of the measured isotopic deviations ($\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ vs. $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$), the measured isotope values of silty soil with 4 % organic matter and most of the soils (except kaolinite) re-wetted with reference water 1 and 2 fell below a water line (WL) with a slope 8.45, indicating that non-equilibrium fractionation processes occurred in the sampling bags during the soil pore water–vapor equilibration process (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2 illustrates that the z-scores of each soil texture increased as the soil volumetric water content decreased from $0.46\text{ cm}^3\text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $0.06\text{ cm}^3\text{ cm}^{-3}$ for both the reference waters. Because there were no differences in the deviation patterns between $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ using reference water 1 and reference water 2 for all soils (Fig. 1), results for both reference waters were combined in Fig. 2.

Kaolinite had the lowest z_{O} (z_{H}) of -1.0 to 3.4 (-0.5 to 1.4) and SD of ± 0.4 to ± 5.6 (± 0.3 to ± 10.8) (Fig. 2). The maximum z_{O} (z_{H}) of 1.2 to 35.6 (-3.6 to 33.7) and SD of ± 1.2 to ± 3.4 (± 1.1 to ± 21.0) was found for silty soil with 4 % organic matter. Surprisingly, silty soil with 1 % organic matter had comparatively lower z_{O} (z_{H}) of -1.4 to 4.4 (-0.2 to 16.0) and SD of ± 0 to ± 4.4 (± 0.1 to ± 12.3) than non-organic sandy sediment, which had z_{O} (z_{H}) of -0.8 to 14.8 (-0.9 to 25.4) and SD of ± 0 to ± 2.6 (± 0.5 to ± 3.9). Overall, all soil textures showed the most enriched isotope values at the lowest soil volumetric water content ($0.06\text{ cm}^3\text{ cm}^{-3}$) (Fig. 2).

3.2. Experiment 2 – Humic acid in soil and water

The z-scores for different concentrations of humic acid (g mL^{-1}) were larger in HAS than the corresponding HAW mixtures (Fig. 3). As humic acid concentrations increased from 0 to 3.3 g mL^{-1} , z_{O} (z_{H}) of the HAS increased from 0.6 to 19.4 (-2.6 to 94.7) with SD in the range of ± 0.4 to ± 8.8 (± 0 to ± 29.4). Meanwhile, HAW mixtures had smaller z_{O} (z_{H}) between -4.0 to 4.8 (-17.5 to 24.5) with SD of ± 0.2 to ± 4.0 (± 0.1 to ± 21.3). Additionally, the pH values recorded from the HAW samples were observed to drop from 8.7 to 5.1 as the concentration of the humic acid gradually increased (data not shown).

A plot of the measured isotopic deviations ($\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ vs. $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) (Fig. 4) shows that the isotope measurements of HAW mixtures plotted closer to the WL with a slope of 8.45 (Majoube, 1971) than the results of HAS mixtures. Two samples of HAS mixtures plotted above the WL, while all others were closer or below it.

The average $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) of 2.5‰ (14.2‰) for HAS was

Fig. 1. Plot of the measured isotopic deviations ($\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ vs. $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) of all the measured samples using reference water (RW) 1 and 2 at different volumetric water contents ($\text{cm}^3\text{ cm}^{-3}$). The water line (WL) with a slope of 8.45 represents the expected relationship between $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ in 100 % relative humidity at 20 °C.

Fig. 2. (a) z_O (-) and (b) z_H (-) against soil volumetric water content ($\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$) using reference water 1 and 2 (shown together and not graphically distinguished). The dotted grey lines represent the acceptable boundaries for z-scores with ± 2 .

significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than the $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) of -0.1‰ (-2.6‰) for HAW (boxplot in Fig. 4).

Fig. 5 compares z-scores with different amounts of humic acid (g) per sandy sediment (g) expressed in percentage organic matter (% OM) at different volumetric water contents ($\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$). z_O (z_H) was largest for the highest humic acid concentration (5 % OM) and the lowest volumetric water content (1.2 %), with 5 % OM showing z_O (z_H) of 9.4 to 19.4 (19.9 to 94.7). There was no clear pattern for 0.1 to 2 % OM, which all plotted relatively close together (with the exception of the volumetric water contents. All HAS samples had elevated isotope deviations for 1.2 % WVC), possibly indicative of a threshold behavior at 5 % OM concentration. Overall, the presence of soil organic matter reduced the accuracy of the DLVE method especially at low volumetric water contents.

To account for the influence of soil organic matter and volumetric water content, Equations 3 (for $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$) and 4 (for $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) were applied to the data set to test a potential correction procedure for soil pore water isotope studies using the DLVE method. As suggested by Gralher et al. (2021), samples with volumetric water content of $0.012 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ had low accuracy due to insufficient water content for the equilibration process. Hence, measured data from this data set were not included in the correction equations. The R^2 values for Eq. 3 and Eq. 4 were 0.69 and 0.70, respectively.

$$\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{predicted}} = 0.74 \text{ OM} - 1.33 \text{ VWC} + 1.16 \text{ (Eq. 3)}$$

$$\Delta\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{predicted}} = 5.46 \text{ OM} - 43.97 \text{ VWC} + 9.29 \text{ (Eq. 4)}$$

According to the results of the multivariate regression analysis, both the independent variables (soil organic matter and volumetric water content) significantly influenced the measured isotope deviations and thus z-scores given in Fig. 5 ($p < 0.05$). The calculated z-scores after

Fig. 3. (a) z_O (-) and (b) z_H (-) against different concentrations of humic acid mixtures (g mL^{-1} , logarithmic axis) mixed with soil (HAS) and without soil (HAW). The dotted grey lines represent the acceptable boundaries for z-scores with ± 2 .

Fig. 4. Plot of the measured isotopic deviations ($\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ vs. $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$) of samples with different concentration of humic acid mixtures with soil (HAS) and without soil (HAW). The slope of 8.45 represents the expected equilibrium relationship between $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ at 100 % relative humidity and 20 °C. Inset shows boxplots of all measured results of HAS (blue) and HAW (orange).

correction were then plotted in Fig. 6. The calculated z_O (z_H) ranged from -5.4 to 4.8 (-10.0 to 21.2). These values were within or closer to the measurement precision limits compared to the measured values in Fig. 5. The z-scores observed using the calculated values were reduced for both the isotopes in comparison to the measured ones. Most of the calculated z_O were more accurate as they were nearer to the

Fig. 5. (a) z_O (-) and (b) z_H (-) against different soil volumetric water contents ($\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$) for sandy sediment containing different amounts of humic acid per dry soil mass (% OM). The dotted grey lines represent the acceptable boundaries for z-scores with ± 2 .

Fig. 6. (a) $z_{O,calculated}$ (-), and (b) $z_{H,calculated}$ (-) against different soil volumetric water content ($\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$) for sandy sediment containing different amounts of humic acid per dry soil mass (% OM). The dotted grey lines represent the acceptable boundaries for z-scores with ± 2 .

measurement precision limits than z_H , which were beyond or below the measurement precision limits. Like the measured values, the largest z_O (z_H) of the calculated values were also observed for samples with the highest organic matter (5 %) and lowest volumetric water content ($0.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$).

4. Discussion

In previous studies, soil organic matter and soil texture were recognized as possible causes of inaccuracies in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ measurements using the DLVE method, but their exact impacts have not yet been systematically analyzed. In this study, controlled experiments using both natural soils and reconstituted soils (oven-dried sandy soil mixed with humic acid in the laboratory) were conducted to determine the impact of different concentrations of organic matter and its interaction with the soil matrix on $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ measurements.

4.1. Influence of soil texture and volumetric water content

The z-scores were influenced by the volumetric water content, with highest ones (lowest accuracy) at the lowest volumetric water content ($0.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) for all soils. Hendry et al. (2015) suggested that low soil water contents could limit the accuracy of isotope measurements using the DLVE method, with Gralher et al. (2021) advising at least 2 cm^3 in 1L volume bags to reach complete water–vapor equilibrium. However, our study found that even with 15 cm^3 of water, silty soil with 4 % organic matter had low accuracy, indicating that 2 cm^3 is not enough if the sample contains organic matter. Such samples with high solute concentrations might be impacted by low water content (Gaj et al., 2019) and high amount of salt (Horita, 2005; Koehler et al., 2013) influence the equilibrium fractionation process. The results of the present study experimentally verify this assumption. Future studies should investigate which organic matter content in combination with which volumetric water content significantly lowers DLVE accuracy to establish a possible correction scheme.

Besides that, surprisingly non-organic sandy soil had lower accuracy than silty soil with 1 % organic matter at low volumetric water contents ($\leq 0.15 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$). While we did not find a similar low accuracy for sand samples in a previous study with pore space saturation levels as low as 40 % (Vadibeler et al., 2022), the results of the present study occurred only with VWC lower than in Vadibeler et al. (2022). Therefore, this study shows that even for non-organic sand, 15 cm^3 of water in the bag might not be sufficient for equilibrium and can lead to low accuracies. Additionally, a direct comparison between different soil textures might be difficult, and if only similar soil textures are compared (silty soil with 4 % OM vs. silty soil with 1 % OM), 4 % OM showed lower accuracy compared to 1 % OM.

Orlowski et al. (2016b) also found that at 8 % gravimetric water content for two different soils (clayey loam and silty sand), significant differences in the isotope measurements were obtained using the DLVE method, high-pressure mechanical squeezing, centrifugation, microwave extraction, and cryogenic extraction. With the DLVE method, the accuracy of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ measurements improved as the gravimetric water content was increased especially for silty sand. Based on Fig. 2, these findings also hold true for sandy sediment used in the present study in which, as the volumetric water content was increased, the accuracy improved. Additionally, Vadibeler et al. (2022) showed lower accuracy when the soil saturation is below 40 % for the same kaolinite used in the present study. Correspondingly, in the present study, with volumetric water contents of $0.15 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $0.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ the accuracy was lower especially for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$.

Besides volumetric water content, soil texture was also shown to influence accuracy (Fig. 2). The DLVE method was accurate (small z-scores) and precise (small SDs) for kaolinite, but accuracy decreased for sandy sediment and both the silty soils as the volumetric water content was reduced. These observations contradict the previous study of

Orlowski et al. (2016b) in which the isotope measurements were more accurate for silty sand samples compared to clayey loam samples. It should be noted that pure kaolinite was used in this study and not clayey loam, which could possibly cause this contradiction. There are assumptions about the influential factors in previous studies. For example, the measurements of clayey loam samples had higher $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values caused by the hydration spheres formed around the cations (Sofer and Gat, 1972). Orlowski et al. (2016b) found that the DLVE method is accurate for coarse soil samples, and Oerter et al. (2014) suggested that soils with higher cation exchange capacity (CEC) could yield biased results. However, the kaolinite samples tested in this study showed more accurate measurements than sandy samples (Fig. 2).

Silty soil with 4 % organic matter and with 1 % organic matter were identical soils, hence they had the same physical properties. But, as the samples with 1 % organic matter were chemically washed, the chemical properties (organic matter) of the soil were altered. This alteration explains the differences in the $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ between these two soils (Fig. 2), and the impact of organic matter on the DLVE measurement will be discussed further in Section 4.3.

4.2. Influence of soil organic matter

In addition to soil texture and volumetric water content, the presence of organic matter affected the isotope measurements of the soil samples using the DLVE method. In experimental set-up 1, identical natural silty soil, which was chemically washed to reduce its organic matter to 1 %, had higher accuracy than unwashed silty soil with 4 % organic matter (Fig. 2). Based on an early inter-comparison water recovery study conducted by Walker et al. (1994), the decomposition of the organic matter was assumed to alter the soil water isotope measurements (Walker et al., 1994). Therefore, the presence of organic matter most likely caused the lower accuracy for silty soil with 4 % organic matter content, but the underlying physical or chemical process cannot be extracted from our data.

Fig. 3 also showed that the soil–water interaction significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced the soil pore water–vapor equilibration in the resealable bags, because HAW had higher accuracy than HAS. Likewise, a study by Lin et al. (2018) showed that the equilibrium isotope fractionation processes of soil pore water–vapor and bulk liquid–vapor are notably different at equal temperatures. The isotope fractionation factors of soil pore water–vapor were found to be lower than the bulk liquid–vapor due to an adsorption isotope effect which is influenced by the hydrogen bonding between the molecules of water and hydroxyl groups on the pore surface. This complex hydrophilic interaction, which exists between the soil pore surface and the water molecules, lowers the equilibrium isotope fractionation factor of adsorbed soil water compared to bulk water (Lin et al., 2018).

Additionally, Fig. 5 showed only minor differences between z-scores of sandy soil with 0.1 % to 2 % organic matter content, with the only exception occurring at the lowest volumetric water content of 1.2 %. Contrary to this, the highest organic matter content of 5 % had the lowest accuracy for all volumetric water contents. This suggests a potential threshold behavior with organic matter interference in the Picarro CRDS analyzer measurements at a certain minimum organic matter content (> 2 %) and minimum volumetric water content (> 1.2 %). As shown by Gaj et al. (2017), soil with high CEC reduces the reliability of the soil pore water isotope measurements. The isotope deviations might also be altered by the exchange of water molecules with the soil particles through the presence of exchangeable O-bonded hydrogen in the organic matter (Meißner et al., 2014), which readily reacts with the reference water that was introduced to the sandy sediment. However, our study was not designed to investigate chemical processes and reactions inducing isotope deviations, and thus, further work is needed.

To overcome the systemic bias in the measured isotope data and reduce the isotope deviations for soil pore water isotope measurements, post-processing correction methods were suggested (Gralher et al.,

2018). Gaj et al. (2017) also recommended a correction procedure, which was developed from different grain size distribution and chemical composition of soil using the cryogenic vacuum distillation method. Wang et al. (2019) studied three different calibration methods for different clay and water contents using the DLVE method. These studies' correction/calibration methods allow for data comparison of soil pore water isotope measurements for various methods and soil samples. The present study was not explicitly designed to derive a post-processing correction method, but in a first attempt multivariate regression analysis showed that z-scores were significantly influenced by soil organic matter and soil volumetric water content ($p < 0.05$). The “corrected” z-scores showed higher accuracy (lower z-scores) than the uncorrected ones. Overall, z-scores for oxygen (z_{O}) indicated a higher accuracy than those for hydrogen (z_{H}), possibly indicative of kinetic fractionation effects being the cause of the lower accuracy that could not be corrected for by using multiple regression. The corrected data showed the lowest accuracies for z_{H} with the maximum organic matter content (5 %) and the lowest volumetric water content ($0.15 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) used. First, this indicates that organic matter is the root cause of lower accuracy (with a possible threshold behavior). Second, this effect became largest when the soil is dry as most likely only a fraction of water is affected by organic matter, and when compared to this dry condition, during wetter conditions the relatively larger fraction of non-affected water can compensate for the adverse effect of organic matter. Future dedicated studies should focus on analyzing more samples with varied organic matter contents and with volumetric water contents to verify if a threshold exists, and if indeed during drier conditions this effect is largest, with the goal of developing a more sophisticated correction scheme. Nevertheless, our analysis showed that soil organic matter and volumetric water content can be potentially used for data correction to improve the application of the DLVE method for various soil conditions.

Our findings demonstrated a critical threshold for organic matter concentration and showed that it is the interaction between organic matter and the soil matrix, rather than organic matter alone, that primarily causes measurement inaccuracies using the DLVE method. Additionally, this study also showed that the measured $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values can potentially be corrected using regression analysis. These outcomes directly contribute to the call for improved and robust protocols for soil water isotope analysis as emphasized by Ceperley et al. (2024).

4.3. Possible influence of rewetting oven-dried soil

Several studies indicated insufficient removal of soil water by oven-drying soil (e.g., Thielemann et al., 2019). A study that argued that oven-drying and rewetting soil might impact DLVE was conducted by Gaj et al. (2016). They argued that clay-rich soils still contain interlayer water or adsorbed water of clay minerals that isotopically exchange with atmospheric water vapor. Despite these previous studies, our results, and previous ones of Vadibeler et al. (2022), where oven-drying and rewetting was used, indicate that the present study was not affected. In the present study, kaolinite showed no isotope deviations whereas sand only showed deviations at exceedingly low volumetric water contents ($0.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$). If residual water from oven-drying isotopically exchanged with the spiking water in our study, it should have affected all samples and especially kaolinite.

5. Conclusion

This study showed that different reference waters used to re-wet the oven-dried soil samples did not control the isotope deviations. The analysis of the impact of soil texture, volumetric water content, and organic matter content on the accuracy of the DLVE method showed that soil texture only had minor influence, and differences in accuracy between soil textures were explained by either volumetric water content or organic matter content. Our experiments showed that especially

volumetric water contents below $0.15 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and organic matter contents above 2 % greatly decreased accuracies.

The most likely explanation found by this study for the lower accuracy was possible soil–water interactions, as HAS with different humic acid concentrations had significantly lower accuracies ($p < 0.05$) compared to the HAW mixtures. As found in experiment 1 using natural soils, also in experiment 2 using humic acid mixtures lower accuracies were related to large organic matter content (5 %) especially at low volumetric water content ($0.012 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$). A multivariate regression analysis showed that both soil organic matter and volumetric water content significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced the DLVE accuracy, and a simple multiple regression model was used to predict the impact of both, leading to improved accuracy. However, more studies are needed to achieve a robust correction scheme in future.

Hence, the soil texture, presence of soil organic matter, and soil volumetric water content influenced the utility of the DLVE method. Additionally, possible chemical processes occurring in the resealable bags during isotope equilibration with organic samples need to be derived. These issues are most likely to have equal impacts on extraction methods as well. Therefore, further inter-comparison studies using extraction techniques (e.g., centrifugation, mechanical squeezing) and the DLVE method are recommended to fully understand the accuracy of the DLVE method for laboratory and in-situ application using wider ranges of natural soil samples.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Devakunjari Vadibeler: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Michael P. Stockinger:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Supervision, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Leonard I. Wassenaar:** Writing – original draft, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Christine Stumpp:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant 509 agreement No 858735 through the WATERAGRI project. We acknowledge our laboratory technicians Ms. Martina Faulhammer and Mr. Wisam Almohamed for their continuous support in the laboratory and field throughout this project. We thank two anonymous reviewers and Assoc. Prof. Daniele Penna for their helpful suggestions and comments.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2025.134081>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

Adams, R.E., Hyodo, A., SantaMaria, T., Wright, C.L., Boutton, T.W., West, J.B., 2020. Bound and mobile soil water isotope ratios are affected by soil texture and mineralogy, whereas extraction method influences their measurement. *Hydrol. Process.* 34, 991–1003.

- Barbeta, A., Jones, S.P., Clavé, L., Wingate, L., Gimeno, T.E., Fréjaville, B., Ogée, J., 2019. Unexplained hydrogen isotope offsets complicate the identification and quantification of tree water sources in a riparian forest. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 23 (4), 2129–2146. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-23-2129-2019>.
- Benettin, P., Rodriguez, N.B., Sprenger, M., Kim, M., Klaus, J., Harman, C.J., van der Velde, Y., Hrachowitz, M., Botter, G., McGuire, K.J., Kirchner, J.W., Rinaldo, A., McDonnell, J.J., 2022. Transit time estimation in catchments: recent developments and future directions. *Water Resour. Res.* 58 (11), e2022WR033096. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022WR033096>.
- Beyer, M., Kühnhammer, K., Dubbert, M., 2020. In situ measurements of soil and plant water isotopes: a review of approaches, practical considerations and a vision for the future. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 24 (4413), 4440. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-24-4413-2020>.
- Biernbaum, J. (2012). *Organic Matters: Feeding the Soil and Building Soil Quality*. Department of Horticulture, Michigan State University. <https://www.canr.msu.edu/hrt/uploads/535/78622/Organic-Matters-figure-6pgs.pdf>.
- Ceperley, N., Gimeno, T.E., Jacobs, S.R., Beyer, M., Dubbert, M., Fischer, B., Geris, J., Holko, L., Kübert, A., le Gall, S., Lehmann, M.M., Llorens, P., Millar, C., Penna, D., Prieto, I., Radolinski, J., Scandellari, F., Stockinger, M., Stumpp, C., Tetzlaff, D., van Meerveld, I., Werner, C., Yildiz, O., Zuecco, G., Barbeta, A., Orlowski, N., Rothfuss, Y., 2024. Toward a common methodological framework for the sampling, extraction, and isotopic analysis of water in the critical Zone to study vegetation water use. *WIREs Water* 11 (4), e1727. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1727>.
- Chesnaux, R., Stumpp, C., 2018. Advantages and challenges of using soil water isotopes to assess groundwater recharge dominated by snowmelt at a field study located in Canada. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 22 (5), 679–695. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02626667.2018.1442577>.
- Gaj, M., Beyer, M., Koeniger, P., Wanke, H., Hamutoko, J., Himmelsbach, T., 2016. In situ unsaturated zone water stable isotope (2H and 18O) measurements in semi-arid environments: a soil water balance. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 20 (2), 715–731. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-20-715-2016>.
- Gaj, M., Kaufhold, S., Koeniger, P., Beyer, M., Weiler, M., Himmelsbach, T., 2017. Mineral mediated isotope fractionation of soil water. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 31 (3), 269–280. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rcm.7787>.
- Gaj, M., Lamparter, A., Woche, S.K., Bachmann, J., McDonnell, J.J., Stange, C.F., 2019. The role of matrix potential, solid interfacial chemistry, and wettability on isotopic equilibrium fractionation. *Vadose Zone J.* 18 (1), 180083. <https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2018.04.0083>.
- Garvelmann, J., Külls, C., Weiler, M., 2012. A porewater-based stable isotope approach for the investigation of subsurface hydrological processes. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 16 (2), 631–640. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-16-631-2012>.
- Gralher, B., Herbstritt, B., Weiler, M., 2021. Technical note: unresolved aspects of the direct vapor equilibration method for stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) of matrix-bound water: unifying protocols through empirical and mathematical scrutiny. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 25 (9), 5219–5235. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-25-5219-2021>.
- Gralher, B., Herbstritt, B., Weiler, M., Wassenaar, L.I., Stumpp, C., 2018. Correcting for biogenic gas matrix effects on laser-based pore water-vapor stable isotope measurements. *Vadose Zone J.* <https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2017.08.0157>.
- Hogan, P., Parajka, J., Heng, L., Strauss, P., Blöschl, G., 2020. Partitioning evapotranspiration using stable isotopes and Lagrangian dispersion analysis in a small agricultural catchment. *J. Hydrol. Hydromech.* 68 (2), 134–143. <https://doi.org/10.2478/johh-2020-0009>.
- Hendry, M.J., Richman, B., Wassenaar, L.I., 2011. Correcting for methane interferences on $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ measurements in pore water using $\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{liquid})\text{-H}_2\text{O}(\text{vapor})$ equilibration laser spectroscopy. *Anal. Chem.* 83, 5789–5796. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac201341p>.
- Hendry, M., Schmeling, E., I. Wassenaar, L., Barbour, S., & Pratt, D. (2015). Determining the stable isotope composition of pore water from saturated and unsaturated zone core: improvements to the direct vapour equilibration laser spectrometry method. In *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* (Vol. 19). doi:10.5194/hess-19-4427-2015.
- Horita, J., 2005. Stable isotope thermometry: there is more to it than temperature. *Geochim. J.* 39 (6), 481–496. <https://doi.org/10.2343/geochemj.39.481>.
- Koehler, G., Wassenaar, L.I., Hendry, J., 2013. Measurement of stable isotope activities in saline aqueous solutions using optical spectroscopy methods. *Isot. Environ. Health Stud.* 49 (3), 378–386. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10256016.2013.815183>.
- Koeniger, P., Gaj, M., Beyer, M., Himmelsbach, T., 2016. Review on soil water isotope based groundwater recharge estimations. *Hydrol. Process.* 30 (2817), 2834. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.10775>.
- Kübert, A., Paulus, S., Dahlmann, A., Werner, C., Rothfuss, Y., Orlowski, N., Dubbert, M., 2020. Water stable isotopes in ecohydrological field research: comparison between in situ and destructive monitoring methods to determine soil water isotopic signatures. *Front. Plant Sci.* 11, 387. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2020.00387>.
- Landgraf, J., Tetzlaff, D., Wu, S., Freymüller, J., Soulsby, C., 2022. Using stable water isotopes to understand ecohydrological partitioning under contrasting land uses in a drought-sensitive rural, lowland catchment. *Hydrol. Process.* 36 (12), e14779. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.14779>.
- Liebhart, G., Klik, A., Stumpp, C., Nolz, R., 2022. Partitioning evapotranspiration using water stable isotopes and information from lysimeter experiments. *Hydrol. Sci. J.* 67 (4), 646–661. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02626667.2022.2030866>.
- Lin, Y., Horita, J., Abe, O., 2018. Adsorption isotope effects of water on mesoporous silica and alumina with implications for the land-vegetation atmosphere system. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 223, 520–536.
- Liu, Y., Xu, Z., Duffy, R., Chen, W., An, S., Liu, S., Liu, F., 2011. Analyzing relationships among water uptake patterns, rootlet biomass distribution and soil water content

- profile in a subalpine shrubland using water isotopes. *Eur. J. Soil Biol.* 47 (6), 380–386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2011.07.012>.
- Majoube, M., 1971. Fractionnement en oxygène 18 et en deutérium entre l'eau et sa vapeur. *J. Chim. Phys.* 68, 1423–1436.
- Martín-Gómez, P., Barbata, A., Voltas, J., Peñuelas, J., Dennis, K., Palacio, S., Ferrio, J.P., 2015. Isotope-ratio infrared spectroscopy: a reliable tool for the investigation of plant-water sources? *New Phytol.* 207 (3), 914–927. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.13376>.
- Meißner, M., Köhler, M., Schwendenmann, L., Hölscher, D., Dyckmans, J., 2014. Soil water uptake by trees using water stable isotopes ($\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$)—a method test regarding soil moisture, texture and carbonate. *Plant and Soil* 376, 327–335. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-013-1970-z>.
- Mueller, M.H., Alaoui, A., Kuells, C., Leistert, H., Meusburger, K., Stumpp, C., Weiler, M., Alewell, C., 2014. Tracking water pathways in steep hillslopes by $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ depth profiles of soil water. *J. Hydrol.* 519, 340–352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2014.07.031>.
- Oerter, E., Finstad, K., Schaefer, J., Goldsmith, G., Dawson, T., Amundson, R., 2014. Oxygen isotope fractionation effects in soil water via interaction with cations (Mg, Ca, K, Na) adsorbed to phyllosilicate clay minerals. *J. Hydrol.* 515, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2014.04.029>.
- Orlowski, N., Breuer, L., McDonnell, J.J., 2016a. Critical issues with cryogenic extraction of soil water for stable isotope analysis. *Ecohydrology* 9, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eco.1722>.
- Orlowski, N., Pratt, D.L., McDonnell, J.J., 2016b. Intercomparison of soil pore water extraction methods for stable isotope analysis. In *Hydrological Processes* 30 (19), 3434–3449. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.10870>.
- Orlowski, N., Winkler, A., McDonnell, J.J., Breuer, L., 2018. A simple greenhouse experiment to explore the effect of cryogenic water extraction for tracing plant source water. *Ecohydrology* 11 (5), e1967. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eco.1967>.
- Picarro, Inc. (2024). *Micro-Combustion Module (MCM)*. Retrieved from https://www.picarro.com/environmental/products/microcombustion_module.
- Pyschik, J., Seeger, S., Herbstritt, B., Weiler, M., 2025. Technical note: a fast and reproducible autosampler for direct vapor equilibration isotope measurements. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 29 (2), 525–534. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-29-525-2025>.
- Santos Pires, S., Herbstritt, B., Stumpp, C., Weiler, M., Stockinger, M.P., 2022. Influence of sample preparation procedures on water stable isotopes in plant organs using the water-vapour equilibrium method. *Ecohydrology* 15 (4), e2444.
- Smith, D.M., 2008. Determination of plant water sources using stable isotopes: a strategic tool for planning water resource management for agroforestry. In: *Management of Agroforestry Systems for Enhancing Resource Use Efficiency and Crop Productivity*, pp. 29–42.
- Sofer, Z., Gat, J.R., 1972. Activities and concentrations of oxygen-18 in concentrated aqueous salt solutions: analytical and geophysical implications. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 15 (3), 232–238. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0012821X\(72\)901689](https://doi.org/10.1016/0012821X(72)901689).
- Sprenger, M., Herbstritt, B., Weiler, M., 2015a. Established methods and new opportunities for pore water stable isotope analysis. *Hydrol. Process.* 29, 5174–5192. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.10643>.
- Sprenger, M., Volkmann, T.H.M., Blume, T., Weiler, M., 2015b. Estimating flow and transport parameters in the unsaturated zone with pore water stable isotopes. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 19 (6), 2617–2635. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-19-2617-2015>.
- Sprenger, M., Leistert, H., Gimbel, K., Weiler, M., 2016. Illuminating hydrological processes at the soil-vegetation-atmosphere interface with water stable isotopes. *Rev. Geophys.* 54 (3), 674–704. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015RG000515>.
- Sprenger, M., Stumpp, C., Weiler, M., Aeschbach, W., Allen, S.T., Benettin, P., Dubbert, M., Hartmann, A., Hrachowitz, M., Kirchner, J.W., McDonnell, J.J., Orlowski, N., Penna, D., Pfahl, S., Rinderer, M., Rodriguez, N., Schmidt, M., Werner, C., 2019. The demographics of water: a review of water ages in the critical zone. *Rev. Geophys.* 57 (3), 800–834. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018RG000633>.
- Stumpp, C., Brüggemann, N., Wingate, L., 2018. Stable isotope approaches in vadose zone research. *Vadose Zone J.* 17 (1), 180096. <https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2018.05.0096>.
- Stumpp, C., Maloszewski, P., Stichler, W., Fank, J., 2009. Environmental isotope ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) and hydrological data to assess water flow in unsaturated soils planted with different crops: case study lysimeter station “Wagna” (Austria). *J. Hydrol.* 369 (1), 198–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2009.02.047>.
- Thielemann, L., Gerjets, R., Dyckmans, J., 2019. Effects of soil-bound water exchange on the recovery of spike water by cryogenic water extraction. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 33 (5), 405–410. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rcm.8348>.
- Vadibeler, D., Stockinger, M.P., Wassenaar, L.I., Stumpp, C., 2022. Influence of equilibration time, soil texture, and saturation on the accuracy of porewater water isotope assays using the direct $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(\text{liquid})}$ - $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(\text{vapor})}$ equilibration method. *J. Hydrol.* 607, 127560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2022.127560>.
- Walker, G.R., Woods, P.H., Allison, G.B., 1994. Interlaboratory comparison of methods to determine the stable isotope composition of soil water. *Chemical Geology (Isotope Geoscience Section)* 111, 297–306.
- Wang, H., Si, B., Pratt, D., Li, H., Ma, X., 2019. Calibration method affects the measured $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in soil water by direct $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(\text{liquid})}$ - $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(\text{vapor})}$ equilibration with laser spectroscopy. *Hydrol. Process.* 34. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.13606>.
- Wassenaar, L.I., Ahmad, M., Aggarwal, P., van Duren, M., Pölsenstein, L., Araguas, L., Kurtas, T., 2012. Worldwide proficiency test for routine analysis of $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in water by isotope-ratio mass spectrometry and laser absorption spectroscopy. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 26 (15), 1641–1648. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rcm.6270>.
- Wassenaar, L., Hendry, M.J., Chostner, V., Lis, G., 2008. High resolution pore water $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ measurements by $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(\text{liquid})}$ - $\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(\text{vapor})}$ equilibration laser spectroscopy. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 42, 9262–9267. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es802065s>.
- West, A.G., Goldsmith, G.R., Brooks, P.D., Dawson, T.E., 2010. Discrepancies between isotope ratio infrared spectroscopy and isotope ratio mass spectrometry for the stable isotope analysis of plant and soil waters. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 24 (14), 1948–1954. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rcm.4597>.